

NEP 2020: ANALYSIS ON USE OF TECHNOLOGY AND ITS INTEGRATION IN EDUCATION.

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Abstract

"Education is the most powerful weapon you can use to change the world" (Nelson Mandela)
Education has been recognized as one of the most important and beneficial factors of national development as one.

Globalization has become possible with the rapid development of technology. Many countries take advantage of these technologies and use them in business, education, and other activities.

Education and ICT is a concern for all schools, teachers, educators, students, and stakeholders during the Covid-19 pandemic.

NEP 2020 aims to improve the quality and GER of higher education, including vocational education. The vision of NEP 2020 is "Use and Integration of Technology" to make India a digital and confident nation, empowering society, and knowledge economy.

The main purpose of this ICT integration is to make education accessible to people living in remote parts of the country. NEP 2020 recognizes the importance, risks, and dangers of using technology to your advantage. ICT-based education initiatives need to be improved and expanded to meet the current and future challenges of quality education for all.

Keywords: NEP 2020, Technology Perspective, Analysis, Technology, Education.

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Introduction:

The first education law in 1968, followed by the second national education policy in 1986 and the 1986 policy changed in 1992, recorded for the first time in Indian history the use of educational technologies (ET) to improve the quality and quantity of education. Education Importance of educational technology. The POA of 1986 accurately recorded some of the previous efforts to use and support technology to improve the quality of education.

Government of India created new education policy. After 34 years, National Education Policy NEP 2020 brings important changes in education. It aims to make education broad, flexible, multidisciplinary and relevant to the needs of the 21st century.

It also seeks to improve classroom processes, support teacher development, and improve educational opportunities for underrepresented groups.

Objectives:

- 1) To understand the role of technology in education from the perspective of NEP 2020
- 2) To identify the benefits and challenges of using technology in education.

Role and Functions NETF (National Educational Technological Forum)

NEFT provides updates on a variety of academic topics that are useful to teachers and students. To increase technology awareness and effectiveness in education, the government has launched a campaign to transform the entire country into a digital society and knowledge economy. NEFT will include new technologies such as artificial intelligence, computer technology, log chains, machine learning, adaptive computer simulation and smart boards. Advice for teachers, business people and professionals.

NEFT focuses on MOOCs, Divyang-friendly learning software, e-content in multiple languages, virtual labs and online assessment and assessment and 21st century challenges.

The four main NEPs we are considering 2020 and the integration of ICT in education.

- 1) - Driver of technological impact
- 2) - Technological impact
- 3) - Change correction of new technologies
- 4) - Recommendations to start in NEP 2020

There is a main work for NEP 2020 Areas of integrating ICT in education.

- 1) Instructional Technology and Assessment Technology
- 2) Continuing professional development of teachers:
- 3) Education (Education for All)
- 4) Good Management
- 5) Promoting multi-linguistic Communication (Eliminating linguistic Speech)
- 6) Educational Access to Divyang students

1) - Teaching methods and observations

Prior to the pandemic, simple PowerPoint presentations, TV shows, video interviews, and learning were practiced in online mode or through different websites, but rarely as teaching or learning resources. As a result of the pandemic, many types of technology have been implemented, with most schools and stakeholders, teachers and students using technology in everything from elementary to advance. Before the pandemic, we didn't know much about different types of technology like WebEx, rising Google meet, but due to the spread in India all schools, colleges, teachers and students and parents have embraced the technology.

Video lectures are easily prepared and presented by teachers and lecturers, some platforms such as IGNOU, NCERT and NIIFT teachers are used to publish lectures. , Various educational portals, radio, internet and educational TV broadcasts on various subjects.

Artificial intelligence technologies will soon be replaced by virtual reality, machine learning, digital learning, 7D, the whole scene will change in the future, policy makers, concerned teachers and educators should be aware of these technological changes and update experiences as needed.

Blended learning, online assessment and assessment of various types of google articles, quizzes and other digital productions. The electronic resource is a web-based compilation of information, images, and projects related to student development. In electronic devices, information is stored digitally on a computer's hard drive or some type of removable media such as floppy disks, compact discs, and CD-ROMs.

Electronic portfolios are a creative way to plan, collect and share works, information, and teach ideas – learning comes with the most subtle personal growth and development. It is the breadth, depth and depth of one's work and achievements. This is one of the best and most useful tests.

2) - Further Professional Development for Teachers

In NEP2020, it was accepted that all teachers working in primary or secondary schools should update their knowledge and 50 hours of continuous professional development is required for teachers. Online education or discussion rather than physical education is more effective and suitable for everyone.

Diksha and Nishtha and NROER and CIET have programs or courses for Continuing Education of Teachers in Higher Education ARPIT and Swayam these two platforms are available

for professional development, all teachers can attend courses to extend their studies in short courses and they are very useful. Many of these programs are available for teacher development. They started a new teacher development program every year through Diksha. Provide books and digital content in digital format accessible to students and teachers.

3) – Fair Education (Learning for All)

Enhancing educational opportunities by providing a variety of resources to people living in remote areas who do not have access to higher education in major cities and who cannot rely on technology, we can reach out these students through recorded lectures and recorded conferences, radio broadcasts & more.

4) – Effective Governance

As we see in the principles of national education policy that technology should be used in education, planning and administration, technology plays an important role in the management of education. Currently, teachers are doing more administrative work, they are given many responsibilities that arise simply from the information they receive, interpreting the information and organizing the information according to this information.

With the use of technology, all these tasks can be done by computers, saving many people's time, reducing the work of teachers, and this time can be used to improve the capacity of the teaching process. , we can manage big data & our data can be interpreted and used as needed. Artificial Intelligence technology is very useful. Even now there are some projects in management education and if we can develop this technology then we can analyze and interpret data, prepare the data and make inferences accordingly.

5). Promoting multi-linguistic Communication (Eliminating linguistic Speech)

The policy makes clear that children understand content faster in their own language (paragraph 4.11), so students will need to learn to use their own language by grade 5 or 8, which will end the study and pave the way for broader understanding. The policy states that the language of instruction in the classroom should be the mother tongue; this requires more investment in language teachers, use of more language learning tools, use of trilingual models, use of good bilingual textbooks and substantial enough importance for classic Indian literature under the "Ek Bharat Shrestha Bharat Initiative" project.

NEP2020 is recommended to use multiple languages, for example content must be available in all languages, language should not affect students, current curriculum is usually English or Hindi.

NEP 2020 recommends that we remove this language restriction by using equal resources because there is a lot of software available for accurate translation, so by using this software one can easily understand the content in one's native language. Indian Institute of Translation and Interpretation will work to translate English into various local languages to improve access.

6) - Educational Access to Divyang students

Technology plays an important role in human development and inclusion. Especially for people with different disabilities. NEP 2020 aims to improve educational opportunities for Divyang with the help of artificial intelligence.

There are many tools, software and training and assistive technologies such as Window-Eye and JAWS for the visually impaired, Head-Mouse Extreme for the physically disabled, text-assisted reading and eye-to-eye communication systems. Senses chat Internet Browser, TOBII Monitoring system for intelligence etc.

Challenges:

- Access to rural areas and disadvantaged groups.
- Knowledge about new technologies.
- Embrace new technologies
- Create new online content
- Get used to new teaching methods
- Teachers always have trouble accessing new technologies.
- Digital Literacy.
- Digital Infrastructure

Benefits:

Helps teachers, bridges language gaps between teachers and students, creates digital libraries, democratizes language learning, makes learning more accessible, especially for Divyang and disadvantaged groups, and facilitates teaching and learning and increases student engagement. It will create good standards for content and technology.

Conclusion:

It is an undeniable fact that the country we live in should reflect the changes in education through the integration of information technologies. Teachers play an important role throughout the process. Teachers can make the teaching process more effective and interesting by using various ICT tools.

NEP 2020 recognizes the importance of technology while recognizing its risks and dangers. There is no doubt that NEP 2020 offers progressive ideas. Recognizes the role of ICT in education, which plays an important role in maintaining the quality of the teaching process.

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